

SEAS exercises revert progression of adult scoliosis: a retrospective long-term study

Alessandra Negrini, Stefano Negrini, Silvana Parzini, Michele Romano, Fabio Zaina, Salvatore Atanasio

ISICO (Italian Scientific Spine Institute), Milan, Italy

BACKGROUND: there are very few papers on the efficacy of exercises in adult scoliosis.

AIM: to verify if the natural history of adult scoliosis can be modified by exercises.
Study Design: retrospective pre-post study.

POPULATION: 31 patients (3 males) of 38 ± 11 years and $55 \pm 14^\circ$ Cobb scoliosis, treated for 3 (range 1-18) years because of progression subjectively perceived (17 patients), or objectively documented (14 patients: sub-group A, previous observation of 10 years, range 1-27), have been included. 6 patients (sub-group B) were observed also after stopping treatment for 6 (3-10) years.

METHODS: 5° Cobb have been considered significant for clinical change. Statistical analysis included paired t-test, ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis and chi-square tests.

RESULTS: exercises caused a statistically significant decrease of $3.6 \pm 5^\circ$ of scoliosis ($-3.2 \pm 4.3^\circ$ per year): 1 patient progressed, 45% improved; in sub-group A results were identical, after a previous worsening of $9.7 \pm 6.8^\circ$ ($+2.1 \pm 4.3^\circ$ per year); in sub-group B stopping exercises caused a progression of $8.3 \pm 3.8^\circ$ ($+1.4 \pm 0.5^\circ$ per year). Best results have been observed in patients exercising since less time, even if some patients continued to decrease their curve during the years.

CONCLUSION: SEAS exercises revert the progression of adult scoliosis, and a prospective study is already under way. The different results according to length of treatment could be due to a plateau of correction or to an increase of quality of the protocol applied (SEAS changes continuously according to new knowledge in the literature). These results question the immediate need of surgery when facing progression of deformity in adulthood.